

Innovative Online Assessment Methods and Students' Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated innovative online assessment methods and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. Three objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The total population of the study was 355 comprising 91 facilitators and 264 final year learners from National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. The entirety of the population was used as sample which infers census. The instruments for the study were two self-structured questionnaires titled: "Innovative Online Assessment Methods Questionnaire" and "Students' Learning Outcomes Questionnaire" which were on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts from the Department of Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation respectively in Rivers State University and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability average of "r" 0.87. Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics was used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-Transformation at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that a high, positive and significant relationship exist between online quizzes assessment method, online discussions assessment method and online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that facilitators in NOUN should utilize adaptive online quizzes that provide instant feedback to students, so as to enable them monitor their learning outcomes and progress in real time.

Keywords: Innovative Online Assessment Methods, Students' Learning Outcomes, Open and Distance Learning.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a veritable tool for nation building. It is viewed as a systematic process of facilitating learning, acquiring knowledge, skills, values, morals and beliefs through teaching, training, research and self-study. Onyali and Akinfolarin in Offem (2021), viewed education as an indispensable means of transmitting the skills and knowledge that are required by individuals to fully participate and contribute to the development of economic, social and political activities of any country. In a similar view, Osuji and Ugorji (2019), deduced that, education does not only improve individual choices available to mankind but also provide the type of skilled labour necessary for individual development and economic growth of a nation. These characteristics of education have made it a crucial index for national development. There is no gainsaying that the education sector of any nation is vital because it provides the kind of knowledge necessary to sustain her citizenry in a competitive environment. This explains why governments around the world invest huge resources towards widening citizens' access to education. Amie-Ogan and Chukwukah (2025), viewed that, modern education system has completely eradicated the space limitation of a classroom by encouraging the participation of more students from every corner of the world.

The provision of quality education to millions has been one of the major struggles facing developing countries like Nigeria. The increasing growth in Nigeria's population, escalating demand for higher education, difficulty of re-sourcing education through the traditional means of face-to-face classroom bound mode and the compelling need to provide Education For All (EFA) irrespective of environmental, social or cultural circumstances have meant that the country must of necessity find effective means to address the significant unmet demand for education (Ajadi, Salawu & Adeoye,

2018). The Executive Secretary, National Universities Commission (NUC), Prof. Abubakar Rasheed, while presenting provisional licenses to some newly established private universities in Abuja revealed that Nigeria now has 264 universities which include universities owned by federal and state governments as well as private individuals and religious organizations (Punch Newspaper, 2023). These universities have practically not met the ever-increasing demand for higher education through the formal classroom-bound learning mode (Osuji, Epelle & Alabere, 2023). This development strongly supports the rationale behind the establishment of open and distance learning institutions like the National Open University in 1983 as a means of improving educational standards and succour for those who missed access to the conventional schooling.

Open and distance learning has emerged as a significant mode of education that offers flexible learning opportunities by transcending barriers of time, space and location. According to Osuji and Bakpo (2022), open and distance learning is a learning situation where the learners are geographically separated from the facilitators. In the same vein, Alaezi in Osuji and Umunnakwe (2022), refer to open and distance learning as educational patterns, approaches and strategies that permit people to learn with no barriers in respect of time and space, age, sex, race, tribe and state of origin. In Nigeria, the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) serves as a significant platform for advancing open and distance education. As the largest single-mode open university in West Africa, NOUN caters to a diverse student population, many of whom are adults with professional commitments and other responsibilities. This diversity necessitates the adoption of assessment methods that align with the principles of flexibility and accessibility. Traditional assessment approaches, often constrained by physical and temporal limitations, have proven inadequate in addressing the unique needs of distance learners. Online assessment methods have emerged as a critical component of this transformation, providing diverse and innovative ways to evaluate students' learning outcomes.

Students' learning outcome refers to the desired learning objectives or standard that students are expected to achieve. Osuji and Bakpo (2022), defined students' learning outcome as the intended goals of a course programme or learning experience that students are expected to achieve by the school or institution. Student learning outcomes represent the bedrock of educational assessment, encapsulating the knowledge, skills, and competencies students are expected to acquire throughout their academic journey (Brown, 2022). In classrooms be it conventional or mediated, students perform their potentials effectively as a result learning takes place. The learning outcomes change the behaviour pattern of the students through different courses. When students meet the expectation of a learning programme, then such students are said to have positive learning outcome, while the reverse is the case when students' expectations are not met. Also, students' learning outcomes have been articulated to include the ability of students to understand content taught in a clear and understandable manner, been able to have appropriate, relevant and timely communication with the instructor, ability to acquire theoretical and practical knowledge, and the ability to think critically. These concerns however are rested on the assessment methods adopted in the open and distance learning institutions like the National Open University of Nigeria.

Assessment is a process of observation and examination through which quality is intended to be tested. Assessment in open and distance learning is carried out online since this mode of learning provides a flexible learning opportunity for learners using varieties of media including electronic print, online printing, study guides, course guides, videos, recordings, software and online information. Innovative online assessment methods are modern, technology-driven approaches to evaluating students' learning progress, skills and knowledge in a virtual environment. According to Cheng and Chau (2018), innovative online assessment methods are essential tools for evaluating students' knowledge, skills and competencies in digital learning environments. Innovative online assessment is described by Malin and Akimov (2020), as a form of evaluation that is carried out using both synchronous and asynchronous methods. These methods integrate emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, gamification

and interactive multimedia to create assessments that are not only more personalized but also reflective of real-world applications (Redecker & Johannessen, 2018). Studies have shown that when effectively implemented, innovative online assessments can enhance students' engagement, provide real-time feedback and foster the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. According to UNESCO (2024), innovative online assessment methods promote student engagement and motivation by aligning assessments with learners' abilities and progress. Hiruni, Dinushika, Chalani, Kerthiga, Munasinghe and Nilmini (2023), noted that, online assessment methods include online quizzes, online discussions and peer assessment.

Online quizzes is a multi-choice or short-answer assessment method administered via the internet to test knowledge, skills or understanding on a specific topic or subject. Online quizzes is a type of electronic assessment method in which students are asked to select the correct answer from the choices listed (Güler, 2017). The relationship between online quizzes as an assessment method and students' learning outcomes has been extensively explored, with evidence suggesting a significant positive correlation. Bognár, Fauszt and Váraljai (2021), asserted that online quizzes strongly influence students' attitude on learning as a result, students perceive themselves as being more prepared for class meeting and more prepared for class assessments. Nicol (2017), stated that, online quizzes increase students' motivation and provides the opportunity for them to revise specific topics to catch up. As a result, students are encouraged to study continuously over a term. Online quizzes are recognized for their ability to enhance students' engagement, motivation and knowledge retention. The adaptability of online quizzes allows educators to tailor assessments to align with specific learning objectives, thereby fostering deeper cognitive engagement. According to Alruwais, Wills and Wald (2018), emphasized that, the interactive nature of online quizzes encourage active learning and critical thinking. This flexibility has been shown to enhance students' motivation and reduce anxiety, creating a more conducive learning environment (Adeyemi, Adeleke & Okoye, 2023). Yusuf and Balogun (2020), stated that, frequent use of online quizzes fosters consistent engagement with course materials, which translates into improved students' learning outcomes. Additionally, the immediate feedback provided by online quizzes allow students to identify their strengths and address their weaknesses, enhancing their overall students' learning outcomes. A study by Kharbat and Abu Daabes (2021), revealed that, students who participated in frequent online quizzes demonstrated improved understanding and retention of course content compared to those who only engaged in traditional assessment methods. Online quizzes play a pivotal role in shaping students' learning outcomes by promoting active engagement, providing immediate feedback and fostering consistent study habits. As educational institutions continue to integrate online assessment tools, addressing challenges related to accessibility and quiz design will be crucial in realizing their full potentials.

Online discussions refer to the exchange of ideas, opinions and information among participants through digital platform such as forums, social media or learning management systems. Cambridge Assessment International Education (2020), referred to online discussion as an assessment approach that allow individuals to engage in conversations asynchronously or in real-time. The flexible nature of online discussions enhance the quality of students' responses positively. It constitutes a valuable opportunity for shy and reserved students to contribute their opinions about a variety of topics, which boosts their confidence and promotes their learning (Onyema, Deborah, AlSayed, Naveed & Sanober, 2019). When compared to a traditional classroom discussion which requires instant replies from students, online discussions afford students ample time to reflect on their answers before posting them for others to read. Research highlights that, online discussions, when effectively integrated into the learning process, can improve students' comprehension, retention and application of knowledge (Arend, 2020). Properly designed online discussions encourage active participation, foster deeper engagement, and ensure that students take discussions seriously. For instance, in formative assessments, which offer continuous feedback, online discussions help students identify gaps in their understanding and improve their

contributions (Martin, Wang & Sadaf, 2019). Such assessments not only enhance students' learning outcomes but also positively affect their overall academic achievement. According to Cho and Tobias (2021), students who participate in peer discussions exhibit better understanding and critical thinking abilities compared to those who engage in individual study. Similarly, Lin and Gao (2020), stated that online discussions promote active participation and equal opportunities for all students to share their ideas, ask questions, and engage in meaningful dialogue. By collecting students' input into the on-line discussion forum, an instructor is able to monitor the students' understanding and use of scientifically sound problem-solving strategies. The use of on-line discussion groups offers a relatively new avenue through which the learner can take an active role in the learning process.

Online peer assessment is an assessment method where students evaluate and provide feedback on each other's work using digital platforms. Obilor and Adegbeye (2021), asserted that, online peer assessment is the process whereby students grade assignments or tests of their mates or peers based on a teacher's benchmarks. They further stated that it provides a structured learning process for students to critique and provide feedback to each other on their work. This process enables learners reflect on their own efforts as well as enrich this reflection by exchanging feedback on their own and their peers' works. Peer assessment provides qualitative feedback that guide and help students in the revision of their work. It helps students develop lifelong skills in assessing and providing feedback to others. It also equips them with skills to self-assess and improve their life (Smitter in Ugorji & King-Agboto, 2023). The capacity to produce quality feedback is a fundamental skill that should be developed in students because it is an essential component of their learning outcomes. Race in Amendola and Miceli (2018), stated that, peer-assessment strategy encourages deep learning by the students; helps in developing clearer assessment criteria as a good way to generate timely feed-back; and it also leads to improvement in students' other assessment practices which enhances students' performance in their subjects. Peer assessment helps the students to understand the deeper sense of the criteria to help direct their learning towards successful achievements. Orsmond (2015), asserted that, engaging students in peer assessment can help them in learning to evaluate their own learning and in interpreting assessment criteria. The findings of Rimer (2017), highlighted that, peer-assessment is used to enhance learning as an effective way to increase motivation for students by engaging them in the evaluation process and encouraging them to help each other to master the topic of learning. Moreover, the practice of assessing others' work against established criteria helps students internalize academic standards and apply them to their own work, leading to higher quality outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the rapid adoption of technology in education has reshaped how learning is delivered and assessed. The National Open University of Nigeria, as the leading open and distance learning institution in the country offers unique opportunities in delivering quality education to diverse learners' population who often juggle studies with work and family responsibilities. Characterized by its openness, flexibility and use of technology, NOUN has embraced digital platforms to facilitate learning and assessments. Online assessment methods play crucial role in this context, providing means to evaluate students' learning outcomes remotely while accommodating the flexibility and accessibility demanded by distance learners.

Traditional assessment approaches such as face-to-face examinations and written assignments, have often been criticized for their limitations in promoting critical thinking, creativity and active engagement among learners (Alsadoon in Dada, Zaifada & Ofie, 2020). It has been observed that while innovative online assessment methods, including online quizzes, online discussions and online peer assessment, are purported to address these gaps, their implementation at NOUN has been sluggish, particularly in Nigeria, where infrastructural, technical and contextual challenges persist. Also reports suggest that issues such as unreliable internet connectivity, inadequate digital skills among students and lecturers, and concerns over assessment validity and security hinders the effectiveness of these methods.

The scarce empirical evidence on the relationship between innovative online assessment methods and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria creates a knowledge gap. This study seeks to address this gap by identifying the strengths of these innovative online assessment methods and how they relate to the students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. Hence, the study hope to investigate the relationship between innovative online assessment methods and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between innovative online assessment methods and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.
2. examine the relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.
3. ascertain the relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres?
2. What is the relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres?
3. What is the relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres?

Hypotheses

- HO₁ There is no significant relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.
- HO₂ There is no significant relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.
- HO₃ There is no significant relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 355 comprising 91 facilitators and 264 final year learners from National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. The entirety of the population was used as census. Two different questionnaires titled: "Innovative Online Assessment Methods Questionnaire (IOAMQ)" and "Students' Learning Outcomes Questionnaire (SLOQ)" which were on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree were used for data collection. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts, one from the Department of Educational management and two from Measurement and Evaluation respectively in Rivers State University. The instruments were tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.94, 0.87, 0.86 and 0.82.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics was used to answer the research questions. The relationship value of 0.1 – 0.4 was counted as “low correlation”, 0.5 denote “moderate correlation” while 0.6 – 0.9 denote “high correlation”. The hypotheses were tested using t-Transformation at 0.05 level of significance with a critical z-value of ± 1.96 . Analysed data therefore with t-Transformed value above the z-critical value of ± 1.96 was rejected and below was accepted.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between online quizzes assessment method students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Online Quizzes Assessment Method and Students’ Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State Study Centres.

		Correlations**		
		Online Quizzes Assessment Method	Students’ Learning Outcomes	Level of Correlation
Online Quizzes Assessment Method	Pearson Correlation	1	.856**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	355	355	High and Positive Relationship
Students’ Learning Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	.856**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	355	355	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 revealed a correlation value of $r = .856^{**}$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres. This result implies that the adoption of online quizzes assessment method enhances students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between online discussions assessment method and students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Online Discussions Assessment Method and Students’ Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State Study Centres.

		Correlations**		
		Online Discussions Assessment Method	Students’ Learning Outcomes	Level of Correlation
Online Discussions Assessment Method	Pearson Correlation	1	.825**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	355	355	High and Positive Relationship
Students’ Learning Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	.825**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	355	355	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 revealed a correlation value of $r = .825^{**}$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between online discussions assessment method and students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres. This result implies that the adoption of online discussions assessment method enhances students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between online peer assessment method and students’ learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres?

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the Relationship Between Online Peer Assessment Method and Students' Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State Study Centres.

		Online Peer Assessment Method	Students' Learning Outcomes	Level of Correlation
Online Peer Assessment Method	Pearson Correlation	1	.837**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	355	355	High and Positive
Students' Learning Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	.837**	1	Relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	355	355	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 revealed a correlation value of $r = .837^{**}$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres. This result implies that the adoption of online peer assessment method enhances students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Table 4: Summary of t-Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Online Quizzes Assessment Method and Students' Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State Study Centres.

Variables	N	df	r-value	t-Trans.	z-crit.	α	Decision
Online Quizzes Assessment Method	355						
		353	.856	31.12	± 1.96	0.05	Ho ₁ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Students' Learning Outcomes	355						

Table 4 showed a t-Transformation value of 31.12 which was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 353. Since the t-Transformation value of 31.12 was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres. This implies that there is a positive significant relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Ho₂ There is no significant relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Table 5: Summary of t-Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Online Discussions Assessment Method and Students' Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State Study Centres.

Variables	N	df	r-value	t-Trans.	z-crit.	α	Decision
Online Discussions Assessment Method	355						
		353	.825	27.45	± 1.96	0.05	Ho ₂ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Students' Learning Outcomes	355						

Table 5 showed a t-Transformation value of 27.45 which was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 353. Since the t-Transformation value of 27.45 was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres. This implies that there is a positive significant relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Ho₃ There is no significant relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Table 6: Summary of t-Transformation on the Significant Relationship Between Online Peer Assessment Method and Students' Learning Outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State Study Centres.

Variables	N	df	r-value	t-Trans.	z-crit.	α	Decision
Online Peer Assessment Method	355						
		353	.837	28.76	± 1.96	0.05	Ho ₃ Rejected Significant Relationship Exist
Students' Learning Outcomes	355						

Table 6 showed a t-Transformation value of 28.76 which was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 353. Since the t-Transformation value of 28.76 was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres was rejected and the alternative upheld which states that there is a significant relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres. This implies that there is a positive significant relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres.

Discussion of Findings

The findings obtained on Research Question 1 on Table 1 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres with 'r' as .856**. Hypothesis 1 on Table 4 showed that there is a significant relationship between online quizzes assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres with t-Transformation value of 31.12 which was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding is in agreement with Yusuf and Balogun (2020), who stated that frequent use of online quizzes fosters consistent engagement with course materials, which translates into improved students' learning outcomes. The finding was also supported by a study by Kharbat and Abu Daabes (2021), which revealed that students who participated in frequent online quizzes demonstrated improved understanding and retention of course content compared to those who only engaged in traditional assessment methods.

The findings obtained on Research Question 2 on Table 2 indicated that there is a high and positive relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres with 'r' as .825**. Hypothesis 2 on Table 5 showed that there is a significant relationship between online discussions assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres with t-Transformation value of 27.45 which was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding is in tandem with Arend (2020) who highlighted that, online discussions, when effectively integrated into the learning process, can improve students' comprehension, retention and application of knowledge. The finding was supported by Lin and Gao (2020) who stated that, online discussions promote active participation and equal opportunities for all students to share their ideas, ask questions, and engage in meaningful dialogue.

The findings obtained on Research Question 3 on Table 3 indicated that, there is a high and positive relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers State and Bayelsa State study centres with 'r' as .837*. Hypothesis 3 on Table 6 showed that there is a significant relationship between online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres with t- Transformation value of 28.76 which was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . The finding corroborates with Race in Amendola and Miceli (2018), who stated that, peer-assessment strategy encourages deep learning by the students; helps in developing clearer assessment criteria as a good way to generate timely feed-back; and it also leads to improvement in students' other assessment practices which enhances students' performance in their subjects. The finding was supported by Rimer (2017) who stated that, peer-assessment is used to enhance learning as an effective way to increase motivation for students by engaging them in the evaluation process and encouraging them to help each other to master the topic of learning.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that a high, positive and significant relationship exist between online quizzes assessment method, online discussions assessment method and online peer assessment method and students' learning outcomes in National Open University of Nigeria, Rivers and Bayelsa State study centres. As education becomes increasingly digitized, innovative online assessment methods have emerged as vital tools to enhance students' learning outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Facilitators in NOUN should utilize adaptive online quizzes that provide instant feedback to students, so as to enable them monitor their understanding and progress in real time.
2. Facilitators in NOUN should structure online discussions to foster critical dialogue and collaborative learning so as to allow students to engage in peer-to-peer knowledge construction, which has been shown to deepen conceptual understanding.
3. NOUN should integrate peer assessment tools within its Learning Management System (LMS), where students evaluate each other's assignments so as to cultivate evaluative judgment practice in them and also fosters accountability.

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